

Survey of Customer Needs and HPC/AI Maturity

September 2025

Conducted by: LUMI AI Factory, 2025
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Glossary of Terms

Item	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DevOps	Development Operations
DL	Deep Learning
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPU	Graphic Processing Unit
HEI	Higher Education Institutes
HW	Hardware
HPC	High-Performance Computing
Hugging Face	AI model hub & library
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
LUMI AIF	LUMI AI Factory
LLM	Large Language Models
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PyTorch	Flexible deep learning framework
RL	Reinforcement Learning
ROI	Return on Investment
SME	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises
TensorFlow	Scalable machine learning platform
Typeform	Tool for conduction online surveys
VR	Visual Recognition
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

A customer needs and maturity survey was designed and launched to collect data on the needs of current, previous, and potential customers of the LUMI AI Factory (LUMI AIF) services. The data to be collected involved current state of High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) adoption, technical needs, barriers, and collaboration outlook. From mid-June to mid-August 2025, the survey was distributed among the LUMI AIF consortium countries Finland, Norway, Denmark, Estonia, Poland, and the Czech Republic, resulting in 40 responses, incl. responses from these and other European countries. The respondents represented a broad mix of start-ups (30.8%), SMEs (30.8%), higher education institutions (HEI) (15.4%), large enterprises (15.4%), and research institutes (7.7%), providing a snapshot of current practice and immediate operational requirements in the rapidly evolving HPC/AI landscape.

The content is structured around survey design, respondents' organizational and technical profiles, and their day-to-day experience with AI and HPC systems. Key outcomes include strong demand for scalable GPU access, unified infrastructure supporting hybrid and cloud workloads, technical onboarding, and specialist support for integrating new hardware or platforms. Access to curated European data resources, straightforward funding pathways, and ongoing workforce training emerged as distinct needs, particularly from organizations scaling beyond pilot projects.

Key findings reveal that AI adoption among the participants is highly mature, with 92.3% of organizations already using AI or machine learning (ML) technologies, compared to 53.8% using HPC. Moreover, 28.2% of organizations plan to introduce HPC soon, demonstrating a growing interest. Organizations self-assess their maturity levels as predominantly advanced (50%) or intermediate (35%), while only 15% identify themselves as beginners. The main drivers of adoption include efficiency gains (72.5%), innovation (45%), and cost reduction. Several barriers constrain broader integration, most notably budget constraints (65%), followed by data privacy issues (25%) and unclear business value (20%).

In terms of technical needs, GPU computing stands out as the most critical requirement (79.5%), alongside AI inference services, data cleaning, and fast storage. Computational tasks focus on AI model training (85%), simulations and digital twins (47.5%), and large-scale data analysis (37.5%). Scalability, fast results, and reliability are the leading performance requirements. Skills and workforce readiness show promising trends: 69.2% of organizations already employ dedicated AI/HPC staff, and 61.5% are actively investing in workforce upskilling. Nonetheless, gaps remain in HPC operations (57.1%), AI/ML expertise (40%), cloud infrastructure (40%), and data science (37.1%). Collaboration is emerging but uneven. While 53.8% of organizations partner with external actors, awareness and use of competence centres and EU-funded HPC programmes remain limited. Only 33.3% of respondents reported participation in publicly funded programmes, while 41% had not engaged in any.

Organizations highlight top priorities in infrastructure access (cloud, GPUs, scalable HPC), large model training and fine-tuning, commercialization of AI-based products, and domain-specific applications (e.g., agriculture, manufacturing, translation). Strategic goals include workforce development, demonstrating ROI, and making societal contributions, such as addressing labour market challenges. The evidence highlights the importance of targeted infrastructure investments, community-focused training, and flexible, partnership-oriented approaches to ensure broad and sustainable AI/HPC adoption across Europe's research and industrial sectors.

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2. Responses

The following section provides the responses of the survey participants.

2.1 SECTION I: Organisation Profile

a. Name of Organisation

Confidential

b. What is the type of your organization?

The 40 organizations represented in the survey were primarily start-ups (30.8%) and SMEs (30.8%), followed by higher education institutes (15.4%) and large enterprises (15.4%). A smaller share was represented by research institutes (7.7%); no respondents from public administration took part.

What is the type of your organization?

39 out of 40 answered

c. What is your organization's main business sector?

In terms of the organization's main business sector, the domain of AI prevailed (42.1%), followed by research and development (13.2%) and manufacturing (10.5%). Other domains, such as software development, engineering, manufacturing, energy, life sciences, and space applications, were represented by either fewer or single respondents; other domains by none.

What is your organization's main business sector?

38 out of 40 answered

Other:

- *Quantum computing*
- *Competitive & market intelligence*
- *Stainless steel hose production*
- *Languages and audiovisual translation*
- *Healthcare*

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d. How many employees does your organization have?

As for the participants' size and structure, just over half of the participants represented small organizations with fewer than 50 employees (55%), while large organizations with more than 1,000 employees accounted for 22.5%. Categories of organizations with 50-250 employees (12.5%) and 251-1,000 employees (10%) achieved a lower participation.

e. In which country is your organization located?

The response rate per country is laid out in the following table. Finnish participants are represented with the highest response rate (35.0%), followed by Czechia (22.5%), Denmark (17.5%), and Poland 12.5%. One response came from Norway, and no response came from Estonia. Answers from non-consortium countries were received from Belgium, Turkey, Sweden, and Germany.

Country	Number of Participants	Percentage
Finland	14	35.0%
Czechia	9	22.5%
Denmark	7	17.5%
Poland	5	12.5%
Norway	1	2.5%
Sweden	1	2.5%
Germany	1	2.5%
Turkey	1	2.5%
Belgium	1	2.5%
Estonia	0	0.0%
Total	40	

f. In which other countries does your organization operate?

In 72.5 % of cases, participating organizations noted that they had operations abroad, with Germany, France, Spain, Poland, Slovakia, Hungary, Czechia, Switzerland, Sweden, Norway, Denmark, and the UK being the most common ones. Respondents often grouped these under EU or Europe, sometimes listing specific Central & Eastern European countries alongside Western Europe. Apart from that, North America and the Middle East were also mentioned, indicating a global reach of the companies' activities.

2.2 SECTION II. Current Use and Maturity

a. Does your organization currently use HPC resources?

This question revealed that 53.8% of participating organizations have already implemented HPC into their operations, with an additional 28.2% planning to do so. Only 17.9% of respondents stated that they do not use HPC at the current state. These statistics show a certain level of experience among the HPC community members and willingness to explore this field.

Does your organization currently use HPC resources?

39 out of 40 answered

If your organization currently uses or plans to use HPC resources, please specify the use case.

- Time series forecast using support vector regression
- Pushing the limits of quantum supremacy
- Medical image processing
- We mainly utilizes High-Performance Computing (HPC) resources to support the development and validation of advanced technologies for vehicles (but not only), particularly in the context of software-defined vehicles like: Advanced Driver-Assistance Systems (ADAS) development, Software-defined vehicle development, AI and Machine Learning integration, Testing and Validation, Sensor Fusion, Scalability, and Interchangeability.
- LLM inferencing
- Development of marketing technology using AI
- Building predictive models, using DL
- We use HPC clusters (IT4Innovations, EuroHPC) for GPU-accelerated AI crop phenotyping, CFD of vertical farms, massive parametric LED/watering optimization, and LCA simulations; plans genome-scale analysis next.
- Planning in production
- Training foundation models
- heavy analysis and model building
- LLM, AI agent, data analytics
- Can't tell about it; it's a secret
- Large Language Models
- Various research projects mainly focused on LLMs and physical simulations

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- *Training AI & running AI models*
- *Innovation for demanding computations for client cases and in-house study.*
- *We operate HPC resources to provide our services to our customers.*
- *AI training, evaluation, and development*
- *We're looking for ways to support translators' expertise*
- *We have our own IT department, and we run multiple applications for internal purposes*
- *AI/ML model training*
- *Training LLMs, Fine-tuning GenAI, GRPO training*
- *Model tuning, model training, reinforcement learning*
- *Currently, we are mostly finetuning GRPO, LLMs on a smaller number of our own GPU cards, as we keep scaling, our own GPUs will not suffice*
- *Specialized model training, running open source LLM*
- *CFD*
- *HPC for research and education*
- *For research*
- *Computational chemistry; Material Science; Bioinformatics, etc.*

b. Does your organization use AI or machine learning technologies?

The utilization of AI and machine learning reported by the participants revealed a whopping share of 92.3% of companies that already have engaged with AI or machine learning in their operations, and only 7.7 % that have not. These statistics confirm the maturity of AI as compared to HPC.

Does your organization use AI or machine learning technologies?

39 out of 40 answered

If your organization currently uses or plans to use AI or machine learning technologies, please specify the use case.

- *Time series forecast using support vector regression*
- *Image interpretation*
- *Already answered the questions before, mainly for ADAS*
- *Personalization and Learning from User Data. The app "learns" user preferences: -which pictograms are chosen most often, -the typical vocabulary of the family/caregiver, -the child's specific communication habits.*

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- *Mostly Gen AI, Adobe's Firefly, Chat GPT APIs, etc. But we've developed our own graphic style converter*
- *Order handling*
- *Predictive models for financial data time series*
- *Textual market data enrichment*
- *AI is the main road between our client and Finland*
- *We use AI/ML for crop stress detection, yield prediction, adaptive LED/climate control, and ESG analytics in vertical farms. Future plans include genome-based trait prediction for optimized microgreen cultivars.*
- *Multi-lingual (EU languages) Gen AI customer support*
- *Report analysis*
- *Training foundation models*
- *language models / predictive text analytics*
- *Voice assistant, video understanding, automated driving*
- *can't tell about it; business secret*
- *Many different use cases within several sectors*
- *Training various LLMs*
- *We are using sensor data of wearable IoT devices to evaluate the health & general state of livestock animals integrated into a management system for farmers.*
- *For everything.*
- *AI computer vision, large-scale video data processing*
- *Largely for software development. We help our customers train and run AI models at scale.*
- *We train LLM-as-Judge models to enhance evaluation and benchmarking use cases*
- *Various POCs have been started. Mainly analysis of grid measurement data and asset management (asset data categorization and modelling). For the future, analysis of simulation models could be possible.*
- *LLM*
- *For additional checks, coming up with alternative solutions, voice recognition, and automatic timecoding of subtitles*
- *We have several areas of AI usage: Productivity, Customer behavior analyses, planning, ...*
- *We currently use standard tools to improve efficiency internally. However, we deliver advanced AI-driven solutions to our customers through the Edmund platform (edmundai.com), specifically designed to optimize and accelerate manufacturing line maintenance processes. We leverage large language models (LLMs) and machine learning (ML) for efficient data processing, integration, and visualization, enabling our customers to gain clear operational insights, accelerate maintenance planning, and significantly reduce downtime risks.*
- *We are an AI/ML solutions provider - we build custom AI solutions for clients across 12 different industries*
- *Yes, we use GenAI heavily for ourselves and for our various customers, ranging from banks, insurance, healthcare, defense, automotive, and municipalities*
- *Tuning of large language models, model training*
- *We are an AI startup, we are creating AI engines, finetuning a set of SLM, LLMs, creating other AI models, leveraging AI agents for internal operations, for SW development, ...*
- *Building applications, CPM servers, training models for satellite image recognition for precise geo-targeting in advertisements, or just doing research*
- *AI for research and education*
- *Research*

c. Which best describes your maturity in adopting AI and HPC?

In terms of AI and HPC maturity, organizations participating in the survey have dominantly described themselves as advanced (50.0%), and an additional 35.0% companies perceive themselves as intermediate, signalling some pilot projects getting started. Only 15,0% of the participating organizations marked themselves as beginners with either little or no experience at all. This data shows a promising maturity level among the HPC and AI community members.

Which best describes your maturity in adopting AI and HPC?

40 out of 40 answered

d. Are your workflows mapped for AI or automation integration?

AI maturity is further confirmed by the share of organizations that have their workflows mapped for AI or automation integration. 44,7% of organizations reported this readiness, and an additional 44,7% claimed that their workflows were partially mapped for AI or automation integration. Only 10,5% of organizations claimed no integration.

Are your workflows mapped for AI or automation integration?

38 out of 40 answered

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e. What types of AI technologies has your company implemented or experimented with?

According to the survey, there are three leading types of AI technologies, namely machine learning (ML) (79,5%), large language models (LLM) (69,2%), and deep learning (DL) (66,7%) that organizations have already formally implemented or are experimenting with. However, natural language processing (NLP) (56.4%), visual recognition (VR) (53.4%), and reinforcement learning (RL) (48.7%) also achieve high results.

What types of AI technologies has your company implemented or experimented with?

39 out of 40 answered

If you selected 'Other', please specify the AI technologies your company has implemented or experimented with.

- *Recommendation engines, Decision-making engines*
- *STT, TTS, biospeech, multiagent, ...*

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f. What are your organization's main barriers to AI/HPC adoption? (Select up to three)

Budget constraints (65.0%) are considered the highest barrier to AI and HPC adoption. Data transfer or privacy concerns (25.0%) and unclear business value (20.0%) are considered barriers of somewhat lower impact. However, all stated barriers to HPC and AI adoption were perceived as relevant, with all options surpassing 15.%. Looking at the barrier of accessing HPC infrastructure, only industry domains (SMEs and start-ups) are impacted; they also share the highest impact on budget constraints.

What are your organization's main barriers to AI/HPC adoption?

40 out of 40 answered

2.3 SECTION III. Technical Needs and Data Management

a. What are your main technical needs regarding AI/HPC?

The question regarding the technical needs reveals GPU computing (79.5%) as the single most important feature, in particular by SMEs and start-ups. Other highly relevant technical needs reported are AI inference services (46.2%), data cleaning and preparation, and fast storage (both 35.9%). Quantum computing (10.3%) is not yet regarded as a strong need.

What are your main technical needs regarding AI/HPC?

39 out of 40 answered

Other:

- Software Engineering

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b. What types of data do you work with?

The data used by organizations is most often company-owned (79.5%), followed by public datasets (66.7%). Sensitive data usage was reported by more than half of the companies, confirming that data security is a relevant need.

What types of data do you work with?

39 out of 40 answered

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c. What computational tasks are relevant to your organization? (select up to three)

The large majority of organizations regarded the training of AI models as a relevant computational task (85.0%). Tasks, such as various simulations and digital twins (47.5%) and large-scale business data analysis (37.5%) or IoT and sensor data (35.0%) followed.

What computational tasks are relevant to your organization?

40 out of 40 answered

Other:

- *Business problem optimization; search for classical limits on quantum supremacy*
- *marketing use cases, real-time graphic generation based on consumer data*
- *Voice-to-voice*
- *Running LLM to achieve as much independence as on big LLMs*

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d. What are your performance requirements? (Select up to three)

Performance requirements, according to the survey, are ranked in terms of importance as follows: scalability (65.0%), fast results (62.5%), reliability (52.5%), high throughput (42.5%), and data security (37.5%).

What are your performance requirements?

40 out of 40 answered

Other:

- *Speed - response time*
- *User-friendliness*
- *Support for modern AI software stack (Pytorch 2.7, flash-attention2, triton) 2. ease/unified deployment (k8s jobs instead of slurm) 3. GPUs with 80+GB of VRAM to fit 32k context size or larger during model training (there is a lower bound to sharding the model layers). 4 Hardware FP8 support*

e. How often do you expect to use HPC/AI resources?

The survey concludes that the majority of organisations engaged with HPC and AI expect to use these resources and tools daily (66.7%), and a further 12.8% of organizations intend to do so weekly.

How often do you expect to use HPC/AI resources?

39 out of 40 answered

f. What are your main concerns regarding data security? (Select up to three)

The most common concern regarding data security was stated to be sensitive data protection (62.5%). Secure data storage and transfer was mentioned by 50 % of respondents and must be considered a relevant concern. Compliance risk (35.0%) and cloud service transparency (32.5%) can be ranked secondary concerns, while IP confidentiality is a tertiary concern. No specific concerns were stated by 5% of respondents.

What are your main concerns regarding data security?

40 out of 40 answered

2.4 SECTION IV. Skills and Support Needs

a. Do you have dedicated AI/ML or HPC personnel?

Almost three-quarters (69.2%) of the organizations already have a dedicated AI/ML or HPC personnel, and another 17.9% of organizations intend to integrate such personnel. That shows a surprisingly good level of readiness and maturity. More detailed analysis shows that all research institutions have dedicated personnel. All start-ups either have or are planning to integrate dedicated personnel. While SMEs show a strong dedication to integrating personnel, large enterprises show a lower commitment.

Do you have dedicated AI/ML or HPC personnel?

39 out of 40 answered

b. What skills are lacking most in your organization?

Organizations have reported that several skills are missing, which may limit further HPC and AI adoption. The most serious gap is seen in the field of HPC operations (57.1%), followed by AI and ML expertise (40.0%), cloud infrastructure 40.0%, and data science (37.1%).

What skills are lacking most in your organization?

35 out of 40 answered

Other:

- *When working with research institutions or corporate partners, the biggest skills gap we see is in deploying our hardware: partner IT teams often lack the network and security know-how to open the right ports or configure VPNs, the dev-ops experience to register applications and manage API keys or certificates, and the database skills. From experience, many other IoT SMEs have big trouble here.*
- *DevOps engineering, web development, to bring a wider array of cloud services to our customers.*
- *High-quality sales*

c. Are you investing in workforce upskilling for AI/HPC?

Most organizations reported they were investing in workforce upskilling for AI and HPC (61.5%), illustrating a dedication to engage even further with AI and HPC. Only 17.9% of organizations stated they made no such investments, while the remaining 20.5% of organizations intend to invest.

Are you investing in workforce upskilling for AI/HPC?

39 out of 40 answered

d. What type of external support would be most valuable to your organisation? (Select up to three)

Respondents claimed that funding support would be most valued (55.0%), followed by HPC infrastructure access (52.5%) and technical consulting (42.5%). Funding support was particularly mentioned by SMEs, start-ups, and HEIs, but not by large enterprises and research organisations. Large enterprises are particularly in need of technical consulting. For Research Institutes, access to HPC infrastructure is most valuable. Skills training and regulatory guidance were mentioned by just under one-third of the organizations.

What type of external support would be most valuable to your organisation?

40 out of 40 answered

2.5 SECTION V. Collaboration and Outlook

a. Are you collaborating with external partners on AI/HPC?

Over half of the organizations (53.8%) reported collaborating with external partners on AI and HPC, indicating that awareness of competence centres and other external actors supporting the integration of these technologies remains limited and should be further strengthened.

Are you collaborating with external partners on AI/HPC?

39 out of 40 answered

If you selected 'Yes' please specify the mode of collaboration with external partners on AI/HPC.

- *Deucalion*
- *Collaboration with universities*
- *MS Azure*
- *Getting resources (including GPU/AI) with L2/L3 support*
- *Cyfronet AGH*
- *IT Dev, building solutions for our needs*
- *AI startups*
- *HPC access*
- *Involvement of various parties during research projects*
- *Google for Startups Partner.*
- *We tightly cooperate with our largest customers to help them be successful in training and running AI models at scale.*
- *Projects*
- *Open research*
- *We are looking into this with a broadcasting company. We are their preferred translation provider.*
- *Consulting, human resources*
- *We're collaborating with Czech universities and their supercomputer centers (e.g., CEITEC)*
- *European projects*
- *Nvidia (partner, GPUs,...), CVUT (access to Ostrava cluster)*
- *Research*
- *Research consortia*

b. What are your goals for adopting AI/HPC? (Select up to 3)

The motivation for the AI and HPC adoption is clear; the majority of organizations seek an increase in efficiency (72.5%). Increasing efficiency is the most important goal for HEIs, SME's and start-ups. The second most recurrent goal stated is innovation (45.0%), particularly driven by HEIs and Research organisations. At least one quarter of companies also highlighted cost reduction, the launch of new services, and customer service improvement. Large enterprises particularly stress the aim of cost reduction and an increase in customer service.

Other:

- *Increase the quality of the translations*
- *better conditions than buying GPUs or provisioning GPU IaaS on big tech clouds*

c. What is your time horizon for your next AI/HPC project?

The prevailing long-term horizon (75.0%) for the organizations' next AI or HPC project signals that they adopt more of a strategic decision-making approach. Only 5.0 % state AI/HPC is a one-off project.

What is your time horizon for your next AI/HPC project?

40 out of 40 answered

d. Have you participated in any publicly funded AI/HPC programs?

The share of organizations that have not participated in any publicly funded AI/HPC programmes (41.0%) is higher than that of the ones that have (33.3%). That confirms some lack of awareness of such programmes among the organizations potentially interested in AI and HPC deployment. The high proportion of respondents stating “not sure” may be reflected in difficulties understanding the question.

Have you participated in any publicly funded AI/HPC programs?

39 out of 40 answered

If you selected 'Yes' please specify which publicly funded AI/HPC programs you have participated in.

- EuroHPC Deucalion
- Cyfronet grant for startups
- PLGrid
- EDIH

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- LUMI test period
- Danish national funded
- Norway's Olivia pilot testing, NTNU's IDUN events
- EuroHPC grant for Lumi-G
- HORIZON
- EDIH Ostrava
- Research Council of Finland, EuroHPC
- PRACE, EuroHPC, LUMI....

e. What are your top priorities for AI/HPC in the next 12–24 months?

The collected statements cluster into six main themes: **infrastructure and compute needs** (cloud, GPUs, HPC integration, debugging issues), **LLM and model training** (scaling, fine-tuning, inferencing, project completion), and **productization and commercialization** (AI-based products, domain-specific systems, startups, distributor roles). Additional themes include **research and workforce development** (trained personnel, researcher involvement, scalable architectures), **domain-specific applications** (agriculture, manufacturing, translation, optimization), and **strategic goals** (planning, ROI, piloting, societal impact, such as labour market challenges). Together, these codes reveal a balance between technical requirements, applied innovation, and broader economic or societal objectives.

- *Launching new AI-based products & services, enhancing existing AI applications, workforce upskilling*
- *Involvement of researchers and leveraging the full potential of HPC*
- *Move more workloads to GPU resources, increase the adopting AI workloads to HPC*
- *Model training, model fine-tuning, model specialization*
- *Train LLM model, launch an online service based on your custom own LLM*
- *To get an overall understanding of the possible benefits vs. costs vs. resources needed*
- *Building our new martech products based on AI*
- *Infrastructure competence*
- *Scaling computations, model training/finetuning, ML operations*
- *Help companies in Europe with our sovereign cloud services for AI*
- *Integration of AI/HPC in public cloud*
- *More GPUs*
- *Building a scalable and cost-efficient pipeline. Due to using multiple pipelines for multiple use-cases, the overarching architecture is the most important topic.*
- *Train and infer the high-throughput large vision model for my brand-new vision foundation model, which I am currently developing.*
- *Use large resources for demanding computation and optimization tasks. This way, we can provide the best solutions for clients and enrich the innovation for the company's own products, which will bring long-term value. (However, we cannot really invest a lot in this other than time, and Business Finland only funds larger companies doing random useless "EU projects" that they, or nobody, needs, etc. Just my experience.)*
- *Anything how to utilize MI250 machines best way possible. The AI libraries develop too fast to keep up with such old hardware. How to keep the latest libraries and programmes listed. How to debug runs in LUMI, while using sbatch scripts and Python, many error messages are not clear at all.*
- *Solve Finland's labour market problems*

- *Creating new tools and workflows for translators and subtitlers.*
- *Scaling AI for crop phenotyping and control, deploying digital twins of farms, optimizing LED/water via ML, and integrating HPC pipelines for ESG and genome-based trait prediction.*
- *Improving data integration and interoperability to provide clearer and more actionable insights from diverse data sources. Strengthening the accuracy and reliability of AI models through continuous learning and fine-tuning.*
- *Planning in production*
- *To be AI AI-driven distributor*
- *Build and train domain-specific agentic systems for automatic reasoning & decision making, data analytics, and intelligent reporting.*
- *Ensure own (on-premises) computing capacity for isolated training, use HPC for larger client ML projects (especially in manufacturing industry projects)*
- *Build a startup*
- *Try out*
- *Easy and cheap access to large-scale, secure HPC*
- *Select a cloud service provider*
- *Take into use*
- *Finish all AI projects*
- *Trained personnel, new use cases in production*
- *Access to GPU HW to support needed LLM tasks*
- *ROI*
- *Use AI for performance gains in HPC*
- *Training LLMs and inferencing*

f. What new data, platforms, or partnerships do you need?

The answers can be clusters around five themes: **infrastructure and HPC accessibility** (cloud, LUMI, quantum, scalable resources, AWS vs EU HPC issues), **AI models, data and applications** (datasets for agronomy, language corpuses, production and efficiency use cases), **business and commercialization** (SaaS models, SME–corporate integration, investment, consulting), **partnerships and collaboration** (suppliers, industrial partners, AI research institutions, policy actors), and **strategy, funding and uncertainty** (external funding, unclear needs). These responses put strong emphasis on **data access, partnerships, and commercialization hurdles**, while still mirroring the recurring needs for infrastructure and scalable AI model development.

- *Partnerships: Collaborations with providers of industrial automation systems and sensor technology suppliers, as well as strategic partnerships with AI research institutions to continuously evolve and refine our AI-driven solutions.*
- *As said, most important for any SME that does not tap a completely new market are corporations with companies with established sales channels. Those often demand a full or partial integration of the technology SMEs provide, which is the biggest obstacle we experience in our daily business.*
- *More high-level services with L2/L3 support connected to ML/AI*
- *Also, a run & distribution environment*
- *Easy-access quantum computing platforms*
- *Access to Olivia and discussion with the NRIS Olivia team*

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- *Data collection, ML models*
- *There are no specific needs.*
- *AI*
- *External funding*
- *Investment, introductions to enterprise, healthcare, government, and defense*
- *We're actively looking for a software development partner*
- *Planning in production, sustainable production, and energy efficiency*
- *Our suppliers are not on the same level and it is making difficulties*
- *AI SaaS Business consulting*
- *CI/CD pipeline, commercial cloud service provider*
- *Access and funding to LUMI supercomputer. AMD platform might bring issues, on which I would ask your experience with. During the years, experimenting with AMD platforms has been more of a waste of time and resources. Nowadays, things are likely a bit different already, on which you could perhaps give insights. E.g., PyTorch support would be nice, if it really worked perfectly... and then of course export to Nvidia-based platforms is still a reality. Cost wise likely a 1000 € of monthly credits for LUMI would be more than enough. If the business case allows, of course, even larger optimizations could be run.*
- *The problem with HPC projects is that clients approach EDIH/University HPC resources, do a project together... and the problem is to then run it, because the client doesn't have the skills and EDIH/University can't host client's projects. Using HPC for the projects where we need it often runs into the restraints of being able to use it only for SMEs/midcaps – it's still often even larger companies that would use it. And instead of the supercomputing centers we've got next door, we end up setting it up in AWS. And while Amazon is certainly happy with this, EU supercomputing centers have a budget they can't access and services only a fragment of the market is even considering using. So fixing this, making the supercomputing/HPC more accessible and not linked strictly to SMEs and de minimis financing, would be beneficial if the EU actually has a goal to use this HPC resources well.*
- *NVIDIA framework, LangGraph*
- *Industrial partners and their data as subject matter experts for applying AI*
- *Easy access to scalable resources to provision end-user services*
- *Audio data, language resources (European languages)*
- *Not sure*
- *Any, but competent*
- *We seek access to high-resolution agronomic datasets, integration with EuroHPC platforms, and partnerships with bioinformatics labs and AI researchers to support genome-scale crop modeling and circular farming innovation.*
- *Data – more open EU transcribed speech data set always good, more per language high quality text corpuses for language specific LLM finetuning also good, access to research partners, access to business customers*

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3. Conclusion

The survey confirms a strong momentum for AI adoption across European organizations, with 92.3% already using AI/ML technologies and 53.8% actively engaging with HPC resources. This underlines AI's maturity compared to HPC, while also demonstrating the rising strategic importance of large-scale computing for organizations that aim to train and deploy advanced models. Most respondents identify themselves as intermediate or advanced adopters, signaling readiness to scale beyond pilot projects.

The **key drivers of adoption** include efficiency gains (72.5%), innovation (45%), and cost reduction, while the **major barriers** remain budget constraints (65%), limited accessibility of HPC infrastructure for SMEs and start-ups, and skills shortages in HPC operations (57.1%). Despite this, almost 70% of organizations already employ dedicated AI/HPC personnel, and over 60% are investing in workforce upskilling, showing a clear willingness to overcome these barriers if appropriate support is provided.

From a technical perspective, the survey highlights **GPU computing** (79.5%) as the most critical need, followed by AI inference services, data cleaning, and fast storage. AI model training is by far the most relevant computational task (85%), emphasizing the need for **state-of-the-art AI frameworks** such as **PyTorch, TensorFlow, and Hugging Face** to be fully supported and optimized in HPC environments like LUMI. Several respondents expressed frustration with outdated hardware (e.g., Ml250) and software stacks, underlining that staying current with rapidly evolving AI libraries is essential for competitiveness.

Collaboration with external partners is already present in over half of organizations (53.8%), yet awareness and use of competence centres and EU-funded HPC programmes remain limited. Only one-third of respondents had participated in public funding schemes, while 4.1% had not engaged at all, pointing to an important outreach and communication gap.

Looking ahead, respondents' priorities converge around **scalable infrastructure access (GPUs, HPC, hybrid cloud integration), advanced AI workflows (LLM training, fine-tuning, inferencing), and commercialization pathways (AI SaaS products, startups, industry partnerships)**. Strategic goals such as ROI demonstration, productization, and societal contributions (e.g., addressing labour market challenges, sustainable farming, healthcare applications) show that HPC and AI are no longer niche technologies, but are being embedded into core business and societal processes.

Segment-specific needs and conditions can be concluded as follows:

3.1 Start-Ups and SMEs

These organizations are under significant resource pressure, facing high barriers in funding, access to GPU computing, and acute shortages in in-house HPC/AI expertise. Their demand is concentrated on:

- Flexible and affordable GPU and inference resources;
- Rapid onboarding, ready-to-use environments, and simple pathways from pilot to production;
- Intensive technical consulting, practical training, and hands-on support;
- Eased access to public funding and scalable infrastructure;
- Partnerships for productization, commercialization, and entry into new markets.

Barriers: Financial constraints, lack of skilled personnel, and data privacy remain critical obstacles, alongside uncertainty about ROI and continuity beyond the pilot phase.

3.2 Large Enterprises and Research Institutions

These actors are focused on scalability, workflow automation, and integration of advanced AI/HPC into operational pipelines. They require:

- High-throughput, reliable compute environments with advanced management and monitoring;
- Seamless integration with hybrid (on-premises/cloud) architectures;
- Support for domain-specific, large-scale model training and fine-tuning (e.g., LLMs, digital twins);
- Data security, reliability, and compliance for sensitive and high-value workloads.

Barriers: Complexity of integrating and optimizing workflows across heterogeneous platforms, the need for expert-level debugging and performance tuning, and the absence of flexible, European-scale infrastructure for proprietary or regulated data.

3.3 Cross-Cutting Needs Highlighted in Open Responses

- GPU access and scalable infrastructure: Unanimous across all segments is the need for on-demand, robust GPU resources with transparent, predictable access policies and pricing.
- Practical onboarding and user support: From first-time users to advanced practitioners, there's a strong call for real-time support, clear documentation, and walk-throughs that reflect real-world workflows—especially for rapid debugging and operational issues.
- Data and ecosystem openness: Many users request curated, open, and high-quality European datasets (language, agriculture, scientific), as well as a secure environment for collaborative projects that involve sensitive or proprietary data.
- Training, skills, and workforce development: Even mature organizations report talent gaps—especially in the operation, scaling, and maintenance of AI/HPC solutions. Custom training, upskilling on new hardware, and domain-specific workshops are high priorities.
- Partnerships and commercial enablement: SMEs seek structured programs for joint ventures with industry incumbents or access to distribution networks, while research entities look for routes to productize or commercialize their innovations.
- Simplified access to funding and operational continuity: The complexity of public funding rules and program eligibility creates a barrier for many, with strong demand for advisory services and more continuous, SME-friendly access models (rather than fragmented pilot/project cycles).

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